

1 **Wearable Devices for Assessing Function in Alzheimer’s**
2 **Disease: A European Public Involvement Activity About the**
3 **Features and Preferences of Patients and Caregivers**

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28 **Abstract**

29

30 **Background**

31 Alzheimer's Disease (AD) impairs the ability to carry out daily activities, reduces independence and quality
32 of life and increases caregiver burden. Our understanding of functional decline has traditionally relied on
33 reports by family and caregivers, which are subjective and vulnerable to recall bias. The Internet of Things
34 (IoT) and wearable sensor technologies promise to provide objective, affordable and reliable means for
35 monitoring and understanding function. However, human factors for its acceptance are relatively
36 unexplored.

37

38 **Objective**

39 The Public Involvement (PI) activity presented in this paper aims to capture the preferences, priorities and
40 concerns of people with AD and their caregivers for using monitoring wearables. Their feedback will drive
41 device selection for clinical research, starting with the study of the RADAR-AD project.

42

43 **Method**

44 The PI activity involved the Patient Advisory Board (PAB) of the RADAR-AD project, comprised of
45 people with dementia across Europe and their caregivers (11 and 10 respectively). A set of four devices that
46 optimally represent various combinations of aspects and features from the variety of currently available
47 wearables (e.g. weight, size, comfort, battery life, screen types, water-resistance and metrics) was presented
48 and experienced hands-on. Afterwards, sets of cards were used to rate and rank devices and features and
49 freely discuss preferences.

50

51 **Results**

52 Overall, the PAB was willing to accept and incorporate devices into their daily lives. For the presented
53 devices, the aspects most important to them included comfort, convenience and affordability. For devices
54 in general, the features they prioritized were appearance/style, battery life and water resistance, followed
55 by price, having an emergency button and a screen with metrics. The metrics valuable to them included
56 activity levels and heart rate, followed by respiration rate, sleep quality and distance. Some concerns were
57 the potential complexity, forgetting to charge the device, the potential stigma and data privacy.

58

59 **Conclusions**

60 The PI activity explored the preferences, priorities and concerns of the PAB, a group of people with
61 dementia and caregivers across Europe, regarding devices for monitoring function and decline, after a
62 hands-on experience and explanation. They highlighted some expected aspects, metrics and features (e.g.,
63 comfort and convenience), but also some less expected (e.g. screen with metrics).

Highlights

What was already known about this topic

- Remote monitoring technologies are promising to improve the current care of people with dementia in several aspects, such as timely assessment and intervention.
- The adoption and acceptance of technology by people with dementia is challenging.
- Several studies have investigated potential barriers to the adoption of the proposed health remote technologies through phone interviews and online questionnaires.

What this study added

- The Public Involvement (PI) activity included focused discussion, hands-on experimentation and detailed presentation of several candidate devices for people with dementia and their caregivers.
- Members of the RADAR-AD Patient Advisory Board (PAB) were given tools specifically designed to rate and rank the various features of the devices presented to them, by order of preference, as well as metrics and aspects of devices in general.
- Each device comes with its own peculiarities and combination of features, so people with dementia and their caregivers need to drive the selection process of the devices to be used in clinical research and future trials, including the RADAR-AD project study.

66 **1 Introduction**

67 Current estimates suggest that there are around 9 million of people living with dementia across Europe
68 (Alzheimer Europe, 2020) of which the most prevalent one is Alzheimer’s Disease (AD) dementia. In
69 addition, the current conceptualization of AD has been extended to encompass the full spectrum of the
70 disease, including both pre-dementia, i.e., preclinical and prodromal AD or Mild Cognitive Impairment
71 (MCI) due to AD, and dementia phases (Alzheimer’s dementia) (Alzheimer Europe, 2020). An important
72 aspect of the diagnosis, in AD and other dementias, is functioning, where current assessment methods rely
73 mostly on self-report and observation by the caregivers. While this information is important, it requires
74 considerable effort and time and still may be inaccurate. Therefore, existing traditional monitoring methods
75 could be complemented by remote, objective, non-intrusive and relatively effortless monitoring, using
76 technology.

77 **1.1 Technology for older community-dwelling people with dementia**

78 The absence of objective data to assess the daily function of people with dementia could be addressed by
79 several advances in digital technology for monitoring and analysis. Objective remote monitoring using
80 digital technology could complement existing methods and lead to more accurate and timely assessment as
81 well as more efficient clinical trials, proposing more effective interventions and ultimately improving both
82 short and long- term care. Developing remote monitoring solutions and adapting them to the needs of
83 people with dementia and their caregivers could, therefore, allow them to live independently at home for
84 longer, support their caregivers and support decisions of healthcare professionals easily and timely, while
85 promoting “aging in place” (American Planning Association and the National Association of County and
86 City Health Officials, 2009).

87 Remote monitoring technologies (RMTs) can include one or many of the following components:
88 smartphones, Apps, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, both wearable and ambient smart home solutions,
89 biomedical devices coupled with analytics. Smartphones, can help assess social behavior, via monitoring
90 calls, text messages or internet browsing, since mobile phone usage by elders is increasing (Anderson and
91 Perrin, 2017), as do the applications of smartphones for health (Joe and Demiris, 2013). Meanwhile,
92 wearable smart devices and remote health monitoring solutions have also been increasing in popularity over
93 the last decade, especially for elders in general and people with dementia in particular (Lazarou et al., 2016a,
94 2019; Megges et al., 2018). More specifically, smart home healthcare solutions can significantly delay
95 nursing home admission (Kim et al., 2017) and promote safety monitoring and care of older adults through
96 mobile devices (Albert et al., 2012; Lazarou et al., 2016b, 2019), wearables (Carrino et al., 2012; Al-Shaqi
97 et al., 2016) and other types of sensors (Mahoney et al., 2007; Mihailidis et al., 2008; Aloulou et al., 2013;
98 Hawley-hague et al., 2014; Stucki et al., 2014; Piau et al., 2015; Lazarou et al., 2019). Smartwatches and
99 wristbands are blooming in the electronics retail market. Their purpose primarily is to monitor daily activity
100 and lifestyle including movement and sleep, in order to promote health and well-being. More research-
101 oriented devices can measure activity levels, stress, heart rate, gait and other vital signs.

102 **1.2 User Acceptance of Technology**

103 While technology seems to be a promising solution, its adoption is often challenging for end-users,
104 especially older people and healthcare professionals. Technology experts tend to select devices based only
105 on their desire to record the most appropriate signals with the highest granularity and precision. However,
106 the same devices might be quite uncomfortable, heavy and too complicated for users, diminishing the
107 outcome and the success of a study, which is particularly important in the case of people with dementia.
108 Thus, the technology selection process should involve both people with dementia and their caregivers, who
109 will daily operate such technologies. The number of different devices and possibilities increases every year,
110 resulting in a variety of factors that might affect developers, such as data heterogeneity, manufacturer
111 communication standards and programming interfaces, but also the end-users, such as shapes, materials,
112 battery life, design, functionality, precision and range (Boll et al., 2018). All these parameters should be

113 considered, when selecting proper devices for monitoring users or for examining the potential adoption
114 from them, especially in the case of treating people with AD. Thus, the feedback from the people with
115 dementia as well as their caregivers introduces a valued end-user perspective in the selection process, with
116 parameters that might otherwise be overlooked.

117 Older people, their family and caregivers can face considerable stress with the newly introduced
118 technological components (Laguna and Babcock, 1997; Dyck et al., 1998; Tung and Chang, 2007). Most
119 of the time, older adults express technology-related concerns, while the perceived benefits of technology
120 might be more abstract to them. The most common barriers in the adoption of technology by older people
121 are: familiarity and access, need for assistance, trust, privacy implications, design, reduced dexterity,
122 precision and physical issues (Fischer et al., 2014; Peek et al., 2014; Khosravi and Ghapanchi, 2015; Liu et
123 al., 2016; Yusif et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2018; Alshahrani et al., 2019). On the other hand, the most
124 highlighted benefits of technology used by older people are: safety, perceived usefulness, independence
125 and reduced “burden” on family and caregivers (Peek et al., 2014). A crucial component to integrate and
126 accept technology in real-life situations (e.g. at home) is to design and develop user-friendly user interfaces
127 (UIs), to facilitate user interactions with the system (Liu and Yang, 2014). In this direction, the interaction
128 of users with technology that takes into account their concerns and preferences has been shown to empower
129 and engage them more in their care (Villalba-Mora et al., 2015).

130 **1.3 Existing Explorative Studies for Technology Adoption**

131 Several exploratory studies have investigated potential barriers in the adoption of RMTs through
132 constructive questionnaires. A recent study, using Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), explored the
133 potential intention of adult children to use online health information for their aging parents (Bao et al.,
134 2017), and its findings showed that they are willing to use such technological solutions. Another study,
135 using TPB, investigated the potential adoption of mobile health services (Deng et al., 2014) and found that
136 perceived value and behavior control, resistance to change and attitude can be precursors for using mobile
137 health services for the middle-aged group, while additional traits such as self-actualization need and
138 technology anxiety found to affect the behavior intention of older participants. An exploratory study
139 examined the attitude and acceptance of women in Singapore, above 50 years of age, towards a mobile
140 phone-based intervention through a phone survey (Xue et al., 2012). They found that the women were likely
141 to adopt the proposed solution if it was considered as useful and easy-to-use. A questionnaire survey
142 identified that the main factors that affect the acceptance of health technology by people with chronic
143 conditions were: attitude towards technology, perceived usefulness, ease of learning and availability, social
144 support and perceived pressure (Sun and Rau, 2015). Another paper-based questionnaire survey found that
145 the most important factors underlying the acceptance of technology by older adults were: satisfaction,
146 perceived usability, support availability, and public acceptance (Wang et al., 2011). Furthermore, in (Wong
147 et al., 2012), the authors evaluated the user’s intention to use different systems for elders (i.e. the Medication
148 Reminder, Dr. Ubiquitous, Sharetouch, and Intelligent Watch), by administering a modified technological
149 acceptance model (TAM) questionnaire. The participants who used the Intelligent Watch showed the
150 greatest willingness and satisfaction, while the ones who used Dr. Ubiquitous revealed little eagerness
151 regarding the perceived ease of use. More long-term studies investigated commercially available RMTs
152 (Giger et al., 2015), showing that the developed TAM questionnaire revealed that the elders as well as their
153 caregivers and their friends responded positively regarding acceptance. Finally, another study explored
154 attitudes and perceptions of contactless ADL monitoring across 15 older people, and found that they would
155 easily integrate the suggested technology into their daily life (Claes et al., 2015). However, various concerns
156 were outlined related to the operation and the pricing of the proposed contactless monitoring technology.

157 **1.4 Commonalities and Differences**

158 In general, exploratory studies so far have focused on the adoption of the suggested technological solutions
159 by older people and their caregivers without presenting them the device characteristics and particular
160 features in detail. Yet, an earlier review study encouraged professionals and caregivers to describe concrete

161 benefits and technological advances to the older people in order to minimize technology-related concerns,
162 while also giving them the opportunity to try out the technology in a risk-free environment (Peek et al.,
163 2014). Another study clearly states that ease of use cannot really be self-reported and actual use is hard to
164 be determined, since the participants cannot conceptualize and visualize themselves using the technology
165 unless they have used it before (Xue et al., 2012). The study concludes that “it may be more enlightening
166 to observe users through focus groups, by trying out a prototype interface”.

167 Based on that, the present Public Involvement (PI) activity involves people with dementia and their
168 caregivers who are members of a Patient Advisory Board (PAB). It also employs a hands-on approach
169 where different solutions are demonstrated, presented in detail with respect to features and offered to
170 participants to test them before collecting feedback. Furthermore, most studies explore either a single
171 demonstrated technology or general features and preferences, whereas this PI activity is part of a device
172 selection process, where several candidate devices were presented. Moreover, in contrast to most studies,
173 the group included participants from several countries from Europe who are members of a PAB of a large
174 European IMI-funded project. The PAB members are men and women with different types of dementia,
175 different stages and experiences, and their caregivers. The composition of the PAB can be found online¹.

176 Furthermore, in comparison with the exploratory studies so far, most of which describe technology to
177 participants via brochures, online questionnaires or verbally, the present study gives the opportunity to
178 participants to experience and feel the devices hands-on in order to better understand and prioritize
179 particular features based on their preferences. Additionally, the majority of exploratory studies have been
180 focused on the older age dwelling population in general and not particularly on people with dementia. Also,
181 in most studies participants completed the questionnaires themselves (e.g. via telephone or given a paper-
182 pencil questionnaire) without someone being present and explaining possible questions. Another drawback
183 of existing surveys is that they mainly provide a general description of several multi-purpose technological
184 devices (e.g., PC, digital camera, video recorder, mobile phone) without including tailored questions for a
185 particular type of a device, applications and features of it, relying the answers solely on the appearance and
186 the practical use of them.

187 **1.5 Aim of the PI activity**

188 The aim of this PI activity is to guide the decision about device selection for the wearables to be used in the
189 clinical trials of the RADAR-AD project². The RADAR-AD project aims to improve the assessment of AD
190 through digital biomarkers extracted from the use of smartphones, wearables and smart home sensors with
191 respective apps and analytics tools. The RADAR-AD trials focus on remote assessment of people with
192 dementia while at the same time offering support to their informal caregivers. Tier 1 of the study focuses
193 on using wearable devices continuously throughout the day and several apps during the observational period
194 and at baseline and last visit to clinic. More specifically, our study examined several diverse wearables and
195 considered also the acceptance or not of particular devices through an open session involving both people
196 with dementia and caregivers.

197 This paper focuses on understanding the unique preferences, needs and concerns of people with dementia
198 and caregivers at the core of a device selection process for a wearable in the framework of the RADAR-
199 AD trials. The selection of wearables presented to the users is not limited only to specific devices available
200 in the market nor are the features and preferences extracted from them. As such, it aims to serve as a guide
201 for any future trial involving people with dementia and caregivers.

202 The process for the PI activity and its steps are illustrated in Figure 1. People with dementia and caregivers
203 first highlighted particular features tailored to the disease, memory and other functional impairments, as,
204 for example, the necessity for a waterproof device or a sound or blinking light notification to remind users
205 to charge the device. Then, an optimization process identified the best compromise between the most

¹ About the PAB: <https://www.radar-ad.org/patient-engagement/patient-advisory-board/about-pab>.

² The RADAR-AD Project: <https://www.radar-ad.org/>

206 technologically advanced and user-accepted devices to satisfy both parties. Thus, the present PI activity
207 described in this paper explored some of the potential concerns and requirements relevant to both people
208 with dementia and their caregivers through a user-centered approach. Additionally, we examined four
209 specific brands/models of wearables and deduced results about participants' preferences

210 This paper is structured as follows. In Section 1, we present a general background about the concept of
211 health-related technologies and other studies in the field of technology adoption from older adults. Section
212 2 provides details on the PAB PI activity and the presentation and feedback collection process designed for
213 this work. Section 3 presents the results and descriptive statistics, while Section 4 considers discussion,
214 limitations, comparisons of results with similar approaches, and suggestions for future research. Finally,
215 Section 5 presents conclusions drawn.

216

217

Figure 1. The framework of the study centered around people with dementia and their caregivers

218 **2 Materials and Methods**

219 **2.1 Participants and Setting**

220 All members of the PAB were members of the European Working Group of People with Dementia
221 (EWGPWD) (European Working Group of People with Dementia - Alzheimer Europe), which comprises
222 of people from different countries across Europe. Its members have been diagnosed and informed of their
223 diagnosis³ and play an active role in collaborative research projects, such as in RADAR-AD. The members
224 of the EWGPWD had all agreed to be members of the RADAR-AD PAB and will be referred to hereafter
225 as PAB members. The PAB was a diverse group composed of 11 people with different kinds of mild to
226 moderate dementia (mainly Alzheimer's dementia, one person with frontotemporal and one person with
227 vascular dementia) and 10 carers from 11 different countries, namely, from the Czech Republic, Bosnia
228 and Herzegovina, the Republic of Ireland, England/Wales, Scotland, Portugal, Belgium, Sweden, Finland,
229 Austria and Germany.

230 Given that the PAB involves members of the public in the design and development of research to act as
231 advisers, providing valuable knowledge and expertise based on their experience of a health condition or as
232 a carer/caregiver, the PI activity does not raise ethical concerns and, thus, does not require ethical approval,
233 according to the National Health Services (NHS) Health Research Authority⁴. In detail, and with respect to
234 those guidelines: i) the PAB involves members of the public for assurances on aspects of the design of
235 future research, making it more relevant to the people it is trying to help, helping to define what is acceptable
236 to participants and improving their experience; ii) the PI activity involves the PAB in the research process
237 with or by the public and not to, about or for them; and iii) the public is involved in identifying and
238 prioritizing research topics, plays the role of a research advisory group, identifies outcome measures which
239 are meaningful and relevant to patients and comments on the feasibility of the research design including
240 the burden of participants and the levels of risk/distress they may be exposed to.

241 The PI activity took place during the 1st RADAR-AD PAB meeting in Luxemburg on 18 April 2019. In
242 total, twenty-one (N=21) PAB members took part. In order to present the devices, support and collect
243 feedback more efficiently and effectively, the PAB was divided into three groups – round tables of 7 people
244 and 1 facilitator – researcher. The three groups were at the same room and were asked the same
245 questions/tasks. The three facilitators were researchers, familiar with the technology and applications in
246 AD. Two members of Alzheimer Europe supported all three groups when needed. We asked all PAB
247 members whether they wished to take part in the session and gave them verbal and written information

³ <https://www.radar-ad.org/patient-engagement/patient-advisory-board/general-members-pab>

⁴ <https://www.invo.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/HRA-INVOLVE-updated-statement-2016.pdf>

248 about the activity prior to the meeting. All agreed to participate in this PI activity, with anonymity and
249 confidentiality by all researchers. The input provided by the participants during the activity was anonymized
250 and stored locally (offline).

251 The researchers explored a vast number of lifestyle wearables and sports wearables available in the market
252 as well as some more research-oriented wearables, paying particular attention to a range of characteristics
253 such as their size and weight (e.g. from light and comfortable size to heavier), more feature-rich alternatives
254 (e.g., several icons and choices), accuracy and battery life. For the purpose of the PI activity, four devices
255 were selected which represented four different combinations of those parameters. To minimise possible
256 biases participants did not know the marketed names of the four devices (they were referred to as Bracelet
257 1, 2, 3 and 4). The accuracy of the devices was known from previous experimental evaluation studies
258 (Stavropoulos et al., 2020). Being representatives means that some devices can be replaced in the future
259 with alternatives of similar properties and features. The selected devices were:

- 260 • **Bracelet 1** - measures steps, sleep and heart rate (HR), high accuracy, light, high comfort, 7-day
261 battery life, monochrome touchscreen, waterproof
- 262 • **Bracelet 2** - measures steps, sleep, HR and 3D movement (XYZ accelerometer), high accuracy,
263 bulkier, soft, 2-day battery life, color touchscreen
- 264 • **Bracelet 3** - measures steps and sleep, average accuracy, the lightest (is a wristband), 7-day battery
265 life, no screen
- 266 • **Bracelet 4** - measures steps, sleep, HR, heart rate variability and perspiration (Galvanic Skin
267 Response – GSR), high accuracy, large and heavy, 1-day battery life, no screen

268 **2.2 The PAB Session**

269 The total duration of the PI activity was around two and a half hours, including a structured voting session
270 and close questions which were quantitatively analysed as well as general and open discussion. The
271 structure and timeline of the session is illustrated in Figure 2. Each activity block is presented in the
272 following subsections. Additionally, Figure 3 shows the setting, the groups and the materials used during
273 the PAB session. The PAB session was organized as follows:

- 274 • Introduction to the RADAR-AD project, the PI aim, current technology status of devices/apps and
275 their potential benefits for the researcher, the clinician and the user
- 276 • Presentation and rating of four specific wearable devices and their features
- 277 • Ranking devices in order of preference and prioritizing device-independent features and metrics
- 278 • Open discussion about the devices and their use

279

280 Figure 2. Focus Group process timeline

281

282

283 Figure 3. The setting, the three groups – round tables and materials used during the PAB Session

284 **2.2.1 Presentation of Current Device Technology**

285 Initially, the facilitator – researcher and members of Alzheimer Europe presented the general outline of the
286 activity aims and the RADAR-AD study context. Then, the facilitators presented all current technology of
287 the devices, while describing the potential benefits for the researcher, the healthcare professionals and the
288 beneficiaries (people with dementia and caregivers) as described in the literature.

289 **2.2.2 Examining and Evaluating Each Device Separately**

290 Afterwards, a presentation on a projector was shown for each device, listing its main features for the user
291 (battery life, screen, waterproof etc.) and its value for researchers/clinicians/persons (metrics and accuracy).
292 Then, 2-3 of each device were provided to the round tables for the PAB members to wear and test, e.g. by
293 trying the touchscreen, checking the time and measurements of HR, steps etc. After the presentation of the
294 devices, the facilitators answered questions raised by the PAB. Discussion followed for the pros and cons
295 of the devices and more detailed feedback was given. For the voting, each participant was provided with a
296 “device card set”, with device depictions printed in color, exactly as shown in Figure 4. This would help
297 the participants remember the wearable devices when they are not physically present on their table.

298 Also, each person was given a “voting card set” with the numbers 1-10. In each voting round, votes were
299 cast – card face-down on the table, counting 1-2-3 and then revealed simultaneously to avoid bias and
300 contribute to fun. More specifically, the PAB was asked to rate every device for each feature from 1 to 10
301 with regards to a) *Comfort* while wearing or living with the device at home (Feature: Size, Weight and
302 Material), b) *Convenience* while charging it, taking it on and off etc. (Feature: Battery Life, Water-
303 resistance etc.), c) *Features* for the user (Feature: Screen with Clock/Alarm, Calls,
304 Steps/Sleep/Calories/HR), d) *Price* if you were to buy it yourself and value-for-money and e) *Overall*
305 device rating. The abovementioned rating was repeated for each of the four bracelets, yielding 20 rates per
306 PAB member. The PAB was then asked why they voted as they did and to expand on the issues further.
307 The total duration of this segment was around 50 minutes, followed by a 15-minute break.

308

309 Figure 4. The four wearable devices provided to the participants, as they are depicted on the device card set

310 **2.2.3 Cross-Device, Feature and Qualities Ranking**

311 The PAB was asked to rank devices, features and qualities by arranging the respective card sets from left
312 to right accordingly (left: most preferable, right: least preferable). Firstly, they were asked to order the four
313 wearable devices from the previous segment, by overall preference. Then, a new card set was introduced to
314 examine device features in general, independent of specific device implementations. They were then asked
315 to prioritize the device “feature card set” (Figure 5 A) from those most to those least important to them:
316 Weight, Size, Material, Battery Life, Water-resistance, Screen with Clock/Alarm, Screen with Calls/SMS,
317 Screen with Steps/Calories/Distance/Sleep/HR, Appearance matching your taste/style, Emergency/Panic
318 Button to call help and Price. Finally, the “metrics card set” (Figure 5 B) was introduced so that they could
319 prioritize the various types of measurements that can potentially be provided by devices from most to least
320 important to them (Physical Activity Level, Steps, Calories, Distance, Heart Rate, Respiration Rate, Sleep
321 Duration, Sleep Quality -Light, Deep). The total duration of this segment was around 30 minutes, followed
322 by a 15-minute break.

323 **2.2.4 Open Questions and Feedback**

324 Finally, all PAB members in their round tables had the opportunity to discuss and elaborate about the
325 potential benefits and concerns of using these devices, according to their personal belief. Then the
326 facilitators communicated the results of all the rankings to the PAB members.

327

328 Figure 5. The feature (A) and the metrics (B) card sets

3 Results

3.1 Device Selection

Regarding the particular device selection, the participants gave ratings (from 1 to 10) for each aspect and an overall rating for each device. Then they ordered the devices by preference. The results from the voting session are illustrated in Figure 6 (per Device ratings) and Figure 7, while mean values and standard deviation are presented in Table 1.

The PAB favored bracelets that they perceived as convenient, comfortable and affordable and feature rich. The most high-rated bracelet (Bracelet 1) was also perceived as the most comfortable to wear, convenient (less charging) and affordable. A bracelet that is light to wear and convenient, but does not have a screen feature was less preferred (Bracelet 2). On the contrary the most feature-rich bracelet was the least preferred due to inconvenience (frequent charging) and despite being comfortable (Bracelet 4).

Figure 6. Average rating per device aspect for each of the four bracelets

Along those lines, most PAB members again selected the bracelet they perceived as the most comfortable, convenient and affordable with enough features (Bracelet 1). A bracelet that is light and comfortable but without a screen was the least preferred here, highlighting the importance for some indication features (Bracelet 2), explored in the next segment.

Figure 7. Preferred order of Bracelets: percentage of PAB members who placed each bracelet in each place in an order of preference from 1 (most preferred) to 4 (least preferred)

Table 1. Order of the devices based on preference (% of Answers) and rating per device (Mean and Standard Deviation)

	Bracelet 1	Bracelet 2	Bracelet 3	Bracelet 4
Rating per Device – M(SD)				
Comfort	7,00 (2,16)	6,00 (2,62)	5,00 (1,71)	7,00 (2,33)
Convenience	8,00 (2,31)	5,00 (2,04)	2,00 (1,20)	2,00 (1,57)
Features	7,00 (2,35)	5,00 (1,74)	5,00 (1,71)	7,50 (2,89)
Price	4,00 (3,10)	3,00 (2,33)	2,00 (1,93)	2,00 (2,56)
Overall	7,00 (1,96)	5,00 (2,10)	3,00 (1,82)	2,00 (2,33)
Order based on Preference - %				
Most Preferred	52,4%	4,8%	9,5%	33,3%
Moderate Preferred	14,3%	23,8%	33,3%	28,6%
Slightly Preferred	33,3%	9,5%	38,1%	19,0%
Least Preferred	0,0%	61,9%	19,0%	19,0%

3.2 Metrics and Features

Regardless of device, PAB members ranked “Activity Level” and “Heart Rate” as the most interesting and useful metrics a device could measure. These metrics were ranked in the first place by 33,3% and 19%

355 respectively. Also, these two metrics were ranked in the 1st, 2nd or 3rd place by more than half of the PAB
356 members. Other metrics which also received votes for 1st place but by fewer people included Sleep Quality,
357 Distance Count and Respiratory Rate (ranked in the first place by 4,8% each). The full order of metrics is
358 shown in Figure 8.

359

360 Figure 8. Preferred order of Metrics: percentage of members of the PAB that placed the metric in each place from 1 to 10 (most
361 to least preferred)

362

363 The most important feature of a candidate device was: “Appearance & Style”, which was ranked in first
364 place by many PAB members (53,8%). This was followed by “Water-Resistance”, “Price” and an
365 “Emergency Button” (19% each), “Screen with Steps & Heart Rate metrics” (14,3%) and “Weight”,
366 “Material” and a “Screen with Calls & SMS” (9,5 %). Notably, “Battery Life” was ranked second by several
367 PAB members (42,9%), followed by a “Screen with Clock & Alarm” and “Size” (14,3% each).

368 “Appearance and Style”, “Battery life” and “Water resistance” were ranked in 1st, 2nd or 3rd place by more
369 than half of the PAB members. The full order of features is shown on Figure 9.

370

371 Figure 9. Preferred order of features: percentage of PAB members who placed each feature in each place from 1 to 10 (most to
372 least preferred)

373 **3.3 Benefits and Concerns – Open Discussion**

374 After the voting and ordering session, PAB members were asked about different existing devices and in
375 particular about the most important aspects to consider when selecting a particular device. Relevant issues
376 were linked to the devices being waterproof, easy to use, comfortable to wear and nice. Many felt the type
377 of information or support the person could gain or have whilst using it was very important (e.g. information
378 about their health such as sleep, heart rate, etc., information about where the person is such as tracking/GPS
379 system, time and date etc.). Concerns about the devices included that the person could forget to charge the
380 devices, misplace it or lose it and the potential anxiety or distress if the person forgot how to use the device
381 or if the device did not work. Table 2 shows the key benefits and concerns mentioned by the PAB members
382 regarding the remote monitoring solutions previously described in addition to any other particular feature
383 they would like to be included.

Table 2. Open Questions and Feedback about potential benefits and concerns raised from people with dementia and caregivers

People with dementia	
Benefits	Concerns
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I'd be interested in knowing what information is being collected • Great to know certain information/details about my health • Monitors heart rate and blood pressure • Beneficial to understand your sleep patterns, sleep quality or sleep duration • Makes your life considerably easier • Gives information about time, date and alarm • The person should be able to receive SMS/texts • It should be simple and cute • Waterproof • Speak the messages and text to speak • GPS tracker and alarm SOS • "Locate/ Find your device" function if the person does not remember where the device is • Locate each other (e.g. I know where my wife is, and she knows where I am) • It should enable people to feel safe when they are on their own • Help me to find my way home • Map whilst cycling or being outside 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It could be intimidating (e.g. the camera) • Worried about maintaining human contact (don't want this to be replaced by devices) • The person may forget to charge the devices, misplace it or lose it • The person may forget how to use the device • The person may feel anxious if the device does not work, stops working, or the person has difficulties to make it work - ideally, someone should be able to access the device remotely and fix it for the person. • The device should be quite robust/solid • Soft material, not make the person sweaty • Color which the person likes • Compatible with other Apps that the person likes / uses • Adapted to native language of the user • Would it work in very cold weather (-32 degrees in the winter in some countries)? • Rechargeable Battery • Can you charge it whilst wearing it? • How long does it take to charge? • Battery life • Device's guarantee?
Caregivers	
Benefits	Concerns
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helpful to know that the person is being monitored • Peace of mind - Reduces worries • Gives people independence • Enables people to live alone • It may help to save money (e.g. linked to delayed institutionalisation) • Believe to be beneficial after some time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having to be a bit knowledgeable to it • Too expensive • Would not want to be observed (myself)

385 **4 Discussion**

386 This PI activity allowed a great deal of interaction between the PAB members who are “experts by
387 experience” and the researchers. The different features any device might have were also presented to them
388 and ordered by personal importance. In this way, the researchers were able to identify and extract
389 preferences and features absolutely important to carry on the selection. The PAB members were presented
390 with different varieties of wrist-worn devices. With assistance from caregivers and researchers when
391 needed, they were asked to rate the various features and to order them by personal preference. The device
392 names were not disclosed for the sake of simplicity and to avoid bias. Thus, the researchers were not bound
393 to select the specific devices presented in the meeting, but rather have extracted guidelines and preferences
394 to select from the enormous pool of ever-changing devices in the market and literature. Exploring users’
395 rating of wearable solutions helps to understand users’ requirements and preferences for e-health services
396 and provide suggestions for e-health system construction. The present PI activity aimed to explore the main
397 factors affecting wearable sensors and particular features and application characteristics acceptable to
398 people with dementia and their caregivers while exploring their preferences. The feedback provides
399 insightful design implications for e-health developers, clinicians and service providers, and several key
400 findings can be derived from this work. From their feedback, activity level, HR and respiratory rate as well
401 as practical elements such as appearance, battery life and the device being waterproof were all relevant
402 aspects to consider. The latter, seemed particularly relevant in the case of dementia due to cognitive
403 impairments and possible stigmatization (in the case of appearance).

404 To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the first PI activities having explored the perceptions, priorities
405 and concerns of people with dementia and their caregivers from different countries regarding remote
406 monitoring solutions and wearable sensors. In accordance with previous studies (Wang et al., 2011; Deng
407 et al., 2014; Liu and Yang, 2014; Peek et al., 2014; Calvillo et al., 2015; Khosravi and Ghapanchi, 2015;
408 Yusif et al., 2016; Hoque and Sorwar, 2017; Alshahrani et al., 2019), PAB members underlined the potential
409 of using the technology for daily monitoring particular aspects such as Heart and Respiratory Rate as well
410 as Sleep quality and daily activity while they stated that they would like to receive certain information -
411 report about the health status and metrics which is consistent with (Steggell et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2016;
412 Klemets et al., 2019). However, none of the proposed features presented was clearly rejected but rated
413 lower compared to the others (e.g. distance count, calories). Feedback from the PAB showed that signaling
414 emergencies (emergency button) was rated highly (as the most preferable feature by the 19% of the
415 participants) and indicated in open questions that they would find it beneficial. Concerns were raised
416 surrounding the topic of battery life, since it was prioritized as the second most important metric. This result
417 is in alignment with previous studies which support that from technical perspective, short battery life was
418 one of the main issue for technology adoption by older people (Chen et al., 2012; Sun and Rau, 2015; Jamal
419 et al., 2016). The wearables in this study range from 1- to 7-day battery life, depending on their heavy or
420 light use of sensors and their purely research-oriented to more lifestyle-oriented purpose. Currently
421 wearables are reaching close to 14-day battery life and prototypes of no-charge self-powered wearables,
422 e.g., using thermoelectric energy to convert body heat to electricity, are emerging. According to the
423 findings, such future developments would highly facilitate assisted living research and practice.

424 Several PAB members expressed also some critical concerns with regard to privacy issues of handling data
425 from caregivers and clinicians, which is in line with (Claes et al., 2013, 2015; Peek et al., 2014). Similarly
426 to other studies, financial costs have been identified as a major concern of people with dementia and their
427 caregivers regarding wearable sensors and remote monitoring technologies (Chen et al., 2012; Xue et al.,
428 2012; Claes et al., 2015; Sun and Rau, 2015). This is in line with the present paper’s findings, in which the
429 caregivers explicitly indicated that they would be reluctant to pay high costs for such devices by themselves.
430 Moreover, it was highlighted also that the water-resistance is of high importance since the people with
431 dementia may not be able to remember to remove it before taking a bath or washing their hands. Also,
432 feedback suggested that some people with dementia may be more willing to accept technology that supports
433 them in their daily functioning, in addition to assessing it. For example many referred to GPS and in

434 particular, to a feature which would help them to track the route back home as very important, This indicated
435 that they would value a digital device which would be useful for the researchers but also to them (e.g. to
436 manage finding their way home and dealing with orientation problems, which is a common problem in
437 people with dementia). Also, the caregivers believed that one of the core benefits from using such
438 technology would be the delay in institutionalization since they would feel safer to monitor their relatives
439 with dementia. Also, our PI activity revealed that personalization, appearance, degree of usefulness and
440 ease of use would be factors contributing to acceptance of technology, a finding compatible with previous
441 research (Wu and Wang, 2005; Wu et al., 2007; Tung et al., 2008).

442 According to the recent systematic reviews exploring the factors influencing the adoption of the technology
443 by older people, among the top common barriers in the adoption of technology by older people is the
444 familiarity and access, need for assistance, trust, privacy implications, design, reduced dexterity, precision
445 and physical issues (e.g. hearing loss), the cost of the device, forgetting how to operate technology, false
446 alarms and how to turn them off, obtrusiveness, low ease of use, potential negative effect on health, loss of
447 control over technology and stigmatization, functionality and suitability for daily use, perception of no
448 need, fear of dependence, limited training tailored to older learners, feeling of embarrassment, autonomy,
449 loss of dignity and social inclusion (Fischer et al., 2014; Peek et al., 2014; Claes et al., 2015; Khosravi and
450 Ghapanchi, 2015; Sun and Rau, 2015; Liu et al., 2016; Yusif et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2018; Alshahrani et
451 al., 2019). Similar to the aforementioned studies, the present PI activity revealed that the appearance and
452 style of the remote monitoring technology is of high importance to them. Moreover, based on existing
453 studies, the benefits of using technology include safety, perceived usefulness, independence and reduced
454 “burden” on family caregivers, perceived need, monitoring their health status, social influence, influence
455 of family and friends and professional caregivers (Peek et al., 2014). However, the strong, positive
456 acceptance in the present PI activity indicates that PAB members might be willing to adopt wearable
457 monitoring technology. Moreover, the participants considered one device (Bracelet 1) as being the optimal
458 solution, highlighting as main features its screen showing daily feedback, its battery lasting for days and its
459 affordable cost (less than EUR 150). These findings are vital since understanding factors of technology
460 acceptance plays a pivotal key role to device selection for trials and research and, later on, the successful
461 adoption of solutions and services based on technology (Wilkowska and Ziefle, 2009).

462 **5 Conclusion**

463 The present PI activity indicated that PAB participants were in general willing to accept and incorporate
464 remote monitoring technologies based on wearable devices into their daily lives. Furthermore, various
465 concerns and requirements related to the use, battery life, features to be extracted, functioning and financing
466 of the monitoring devices have to be considered, since they might hinder acceptance of the technology. To
467 the best of our knowledge, no prior PI activities have investigated different perspectives among several
468 people in dementia and pre-dementia stages as well as caregivers across different countries in Europe.
469 Moreover, it has been conducted through face-to-face contact and not by telephone interviews, where time
470 length is a critical limitation. In addition, the PAB had the opportunity to explore the particular features of
471 each device hands-on, to interact with them and have their features and metrics explained to maximize their
472 potential to understanding them and their potential benefits and pitfalls. A systematic way for the PAB to
473 provide feedback in a straightforward and measurable manner was devised using cards, to rate and order
474 features and devices by preference. By considering their feedback, future research design and clinical
475 practice, researchers, technology developers as well as policy makers and professional caregivers can
476 promote the acceptance and implementation of remote monitoring in the care of people with dementia. As
477 the PI activity was conducted in the framework of the RADAR-AD research project, its valuable insights
478 were already used to support important decisions related to its ongoing developments and mainly the choice
479 of devices to be used in prospective European remote monitoring cohort study with research participants
480 from pre-dementia to dementia stages. A positive impact on the recruitment, retention and wellbeing of the
481 RADAR-AD research participants is expected, demonstrating the importance of PI in dementia research.

482

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